

THE HISTORY OF THE LITERARY NIGHTS OF THE POET SAYID
ABDULAHADKHAN, THE RULER OF BUKHARA EMIRATE

Sherxon Qorayev,

"TIQXMMI" National Research University

Associate Professor of the Institute of Irrigation and Agro-Technology,
doctor of philosophy (PhD) in philological sciences.

ABSTRACT

This scientific article is devoted to the work of the emir of Bukhara and the poet of rulers, Abdulahad Khan, court literature, and the history of literary evenings held in the presence of the emir.

Poets gathered around the ruling poet Abdulahad Khan and spent literary evenings. This served the development of literature and art in the khanate.

Keywords: Palace poets, literary environment, tazkiras, master poet, mushairas.

Enter. It is known that at the beginning of the XIX and XX centuries, a unique literary atmosphere was formed in the palaces of the khans of Khiva, Ko'kan, and Bukhara. In particular, the emirs of Bukhara were surrounded by representatives of the literary environment - many talented poets, and with their participation, regular mushaira evenings were organized in the palace.

Main text. The son of the Bukhara emir Muzaffar Khan ruled from 1885 to 1910, the great poet Abdulahad Khan (1859-1911) also wrote Persian-Tajik and Uzbek poems under the pseudonym "Ojiz" and read his poems at literary gatherings. The poet of the rulers created a cabinet. However, historian H. Toraev said that Abdulahad Khan, the seventh ruler of the Mangit dynasty, did not establish a devan.

*Қил мурувват ҳолима эй хўбларнинг сарвари,
Токи бўлғай меҳнату андуҳ ҳижрондин нари,
Ожизи бечорага кўрсат юзингнинг ахтари,
Чехра кўрсат қилма истиғно Амирга эй пари,
Кўрмаса бир дам қачон сабру қарори бор экан.*

Amir Abdulahad Khan (as mentioned above) attached praises to a number of ghazals of

Kokan Khan Umar Khan Amiri [1, B. 460]. Poet Ojiz Mulla also wrote a response to Sharif Anbar's Persian-Tajik ghazal:

Ҳалли мушкилҳо, зи лутфи ҳайи акбар ёфтам,

Ҳосили мақсуд аз роҳи наёмбар ёфтам.

Ў зи рӯйи осмон гуфто – вумо тахти фалак,

Соли таърихаи чунун аз машқи Анбар ёфтам.

(Content: I found the solution to my problems from the grace of God, I found the fruit of my goals from the way of the prophet. He said from the face of the sky, we are under the sky, I found the year of history from the exercise of Anbar.)

It seems that in the poem of the poet Anbar, a date is given in the abjad method, which Amir cleverly and tastefully expressed in verse. [<https://m.facebook.com/726997644080431>].

Amir Abdulahad Khan was one of the most famous poets of his time. Muhammad Ali Baljuvani in his work "Tarihi nofeiy" called the ruling poet "the sultan of the age, the poet of the era, the nightingale city [2, B. 44]" admitted. Therefore, it is noted in the sources that "the nightingale of virtue and good fortune" was a tall, lofty poet of his time, he wrote good poetry, could say heartfelt words, and was the only one of his time in story writing. His verses and verses have reached us. For example, "Tazkirat ush-share" compiled by Haji Ne'matillo Mukhtaram on the order of this emir contains examples of his poems [3, B. 110].

Amir Abdulahad Khan was a very educated and intelligent person. In addition to Uzbek, he knew Persian and Russian perfectly. He could also speak French. He recited the Qur'an in Arabic. Amir Sayyid Abdulahad studied jurisprudence, logic, and philosophy from the masters of his time, and also gained deep knowledge in the field of literature. The fact that Amir Abdulahad Khan was a cultured, enlightened, and just ruler is also mentioned in Sadriddin Aini's book "Esdaliker" and Afzal Pirmasti's "Tazkirat ush-shuaro" [<https://m.facebook.com/726997644080431>].

The receptions in the palaces of the Amir in the cities of Bukhara, Karmana, and Shahrisabz were conducted in two languages. According to the book "Uzbek Literature of the National Renaissance", "Traditional bilingualism continued in the literary environment of Bukhara during this period. Amir Abdulahad Khan (1859-1910) was the most notable representative not only of political life, but also of literary life. This was especially evident during his Emirate period (1885-1910). The closeness of the Sahibdevan ruler poet to literature was to such an extent that some district governors, for example, the governor of Hisar, Avliyokulibek, organized a devan with the nickname "Husayni". Other governors also wrote

poems to look good to the emir[5, B.13].

The palace of Ruler Abdulahad Khan was always full of virtuous people, poets, and writers[4, B.68]. During his rule, he gathered intellectuals and representatives of science and literature around him. He did not miss the material and moral support of literature and art lovers. Literary critic Shuhrat Khalilov writes that many poets, such as Afzal Pirmasti, Mulla Sharif Anbar, Mirza Shamsiddin Doi, and Muhammad Aminkhoja Eshon, created in the emir's palace and under the auspices and recited poems at mushaira nights. In their work, supplication to Allah, depiction of a lover, and praise of (the ruler) are visible. "With the encouragement and efforts of Abdullah Khan, poets such as Afzal Pirmasti (1915 AD), Ne'matulla Mukhtaram (1920 AD), Mirsiddiq Hashmat (Amir's brother), Abdi created tazkiras and renewed traditional tazkiras with new works. those who enriched [5, B.14]". According to information, the tazkirah "Afzali ut tazkor fi zikrish shuaro wal ash'or" ("Afzal tazkiras about poets and poems") compiled by Afzal Makhdum Pirmasti contains information about 135 poets who lived and created in the late XIX and early XX centuries. During this period, several tazkiras were created, and traditional tazkiranavis were enriched with new works. In particular, the Tazkirat "Tazkirat ush-share" written by the prince of Bukhara, Said Mir Muhammad Siddiq Hashmat, talks about more than 60 poets who lived in the emirate, their nicknames, biographies, and famous poems. "Tazkirai shuaro Abdulazim Shariy" written by Haji Abdulazim Shariy talks about poets and scientists who lived and worked in Bukhara, Samarkand, and Tashkent at the end of the XIX century. Nematullah Mukhtaram's Tazkirai "Tazkirai Haji Nematullah Mukhtaram", written in Persian, contains information about the pseudonyms, names, surnames, and works of poets who lived in Bukhara in the XIX and early XX centuries. Abdiy Mirabdullahhoja's takers "Tazkirai Abdiy" (Or "Tazkirat ush-share mutaaxhirini Bukhara") and "Tazkirat ush-share" (1904) contain information about 118 poets who lived and created during the era of Amir Abdulahad [<https://www.bukhara. en/?p=12632>].

It is reported that Mirza Somi, the court poet and historian, "*was banished from Abdulahad Khan's palace when he was old.*" *He tried hard to return to the palace and restore his previous position. Amir, who likes to travel and writes books about his travels, turns the work of the Arab writer Husayn al-Tavirani about travel and dedicates the translation to Abdulahad. In addition, he follows the same path with his work "Mirat al-khayol". At the beginning, end and special chapters of his work, Amir praises Abdulahad:*

Вале махдуми ман шахсест доно,

Суханро назди у қадрест воло.

Дилаш аз гармийи маъни ба чўш аст,

Рауф асту ҳалиму айбнўш аст. [https://www.bukhari.uz/?p=15879].

According to the information, hundreds of poets such as Mirza Somi were created in Abdulahad Khan's palace, and poetry evenings were organized under the leadership of the ruler's poet.

Also, Amir wrote in a diary the details of "Abdullah Khan's trip to Russia during December 1892 - February 1893. This diary was published by Ismoilbek Gasprinsky in Kazan in 1894 under the title "Diary of His Highness the Emir of Bukhara"[6, B.128]. This work was published in 1998 "Social opinion. Published in Uzbek in issues 3-4 of "Human Rights" magazine [https://www.bukhara.uz/?p=12632].

To sum up, the literary atmosphere in the palace of the emir of Bukhara, Abdulahad Khan, and the literary evenings held in his presence served the development of our classic literature and art.

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